

The 3 best exercises for your trapeze training

The fitness trainer, [TJ Leo](#) shares the 3 best exercises for your trapeze training.

According to TJ Leo, the trapeziums, such as the forearms, do not usually train regularly, but they are an important muscle to look better aesthetically and avoid neck and cervical injuries.

Trapezoids, such as twins or forearms are the great forgotten by many fitness athletes who, decline to train them, by exercising them secondarily in other exercises such as the military shoulder press, squats, biceps curls or dominated. So today, TJ Leo tells you some exercises to develop your trapezoids and look better aesthetically and more proportionate.

1- Rowing around the neck

With barbell or dumbbell and even pulley, according to [the experienced fitness trainer](#), TJ Leo, it is an excellent movement to exercise the middle deltoid and, depending on the type of grip, also the trapeze. To involve this muscle, make a narrower grip by clasping your hands on the bar, raising it to the chin with your elbows as high as possible. When going down, do it with control avoiding jerks.

2- Shrugs

Like rowing on the neck, it can be done with barbell or dumbbell. As TJ Leo argues, the fundamental thing in both cases, quick grip, fully stretched arms and lift the shoulders as much as possible, holding the contraction up a second or two. Of course, avoid arching your back or helping the movement with the lower train, since it is about isolating the trapezoid as much as possible.

3- Farmer's steps

Although it is very useful for working the whole body, according to [the academic publications](#) of TJ Leo, it is an ideal exercise to bring strength to our trapezes. Its execution is easy: grab two important weights, one in each hand, and transport them for a few meters. The more distance, the more the trapezoids will burn ... The moment you notice that your back arches or you lose your balance, brake, rest and start the march again. And always look straight ahead.